

Deep Learning Based Normal Behaviour Modelling for a Cereal Double Screw Extruder

Anthony Mashava¹ (✉), Tirivangani Magadza², Ediger Mutevani³

¹ Harare Institute of Technology, Harare, Zimbabwe

✉ mashavaa@gmail.com | ☎ +263 77 321 3982

² Harare Institute of Technology, Harare, Zimbabwe

✉ tmagadza@hit.ac.zw | ☎ +263 77 501 8409

³ Harare Institute of Technology, Harare, Zimbabwe

✉ dmutevani@hit.ac.zw | ☎ +263 77 330 1456

ABSTRACT

Normal Behavior Modeling (NBM) is an artificial intelligence technique that is used to determine baseline-normalcy of an equipment or process in relation to predictive maintenance and anomaly detection. The Cereal Double Screw Extruder (CDSE) stands notably as a critical and sophisticated Equipment for a Cereal Processing line. The ability to accurately understand the machine performance at any given time is key to sustainability of the equipment and the overall process. For a Deep Learning (DL) NBM using SCADA time series data, RNN and their variants were used. The three architectures of interest were RNN, RNN-LSTM and RNN-LSTM-DAE. The lowest overall reconstruction loss was achieved with RNN-LSTM-DAE with overall reconstruction loss of 1.0007×10^{-4} . The same model also had the lowest reconstruction losses of Critical Response Variables (CRVs). The Model, with given thresholds of CRVs of 0.04, 0.02, 0.02 and 0.1 for Main Motor Amperage, Gearbox Temperature, Barrel Section_2 Temperature and Barrel Section_3 Temperature CRVs respectively, was able to pick all known anomalies.

Key Words: Cereal Double Screw Extruder, Critical Response Variables, Normal Behavior Modeling, Anomaly detection, data reconstruction, reconstruction loss, deep learning.

INTRODUCTION

Extrusion is the technology that is used to process more than half of breakfast cereals worldwide. It is a multi-billion dollar industry globally, due to its effectiveness in cereal production, (Mitra & Hosahalli, 2021). The technology has gained popularity in the recent age, and various automation and data acquiring versions being introduced in past decade (Sule, et al., 2024). One of the extruder capable of acquiring processing data is model M200. The model used SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition), a computer based system that monitors and controls the industrial processes, (Sule, et al., 2024). The key data monitored on a model (M200) are main motor amperage, gear box temperature, barrel pressure and sectionalised barrel temperatures (Choton et al., 2020).

Cite This Paper: Anthony Mashava(✉), Tirivangani Magadza and Ediger Mutevani(2025). "Deep Learning Based Normal Behavior Modeling for a Cereal Double Screw Extruder". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ENGINEERING AND DEVELOPMENT (IJETED)* ISSN 2249-6149, vol. 15, no. 4, 2025, pp. 74-84. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15869689>

The use of SCADA gives an opportunity for various machine learning and deep learning to be carried out on a Cereal Double Screw Extruder (CDSE). One of the artificial intelligence systems that can be implemented is a Normal Behaviour Modelling (NBM). This is achieved through training deep neural networks with a lot of (CDSE) normal processing data. Once the training is done and thresholds defined, the model will be capable of detecting process anomalies, minimising the chances of breakdowns, through predictive maintenance.

Extrusion Process

Extruders are delicate equipment's but critical to the extrusion process. Proper maintenance of the equipment is important for continuous production. The machine comes with important variables that need to be continuously checked to ensure an effective and efficient production process. The cost that is associated with the extruder breakdown is left and can result in shut down of a Factory. The critical components that are constantly checked by the SCADA for well-being are the main motor, gearbox and the sectionalised barrel.

CDSE double screws are rotated through the gearbox by a main motor (Choton et al., 2020). The motor is generally huge in nature to be able to turn feed of around from couple hundreds of kilograms to tonnes per hour. The gearboxes are also critical and generate the required torque (Lee et al., 2023). These components are mostly imported, extremely expensive to transport by air and time consuming to transport by sea. The barrel is pressure cooker where the processing happens, and temperature monitoring is imperative to indicate the state of the cooking (Choton et al., 2020). All the critical components indicated are generally expensive, and due to supply chain challenges, the down time can take several months. This leads to the need of a predictive maintenance tool that can indicate in real time, possible challenges emanating from critical components (Lee et al., 2023).

Figure 1 CDSE Machine

Normal Behaviour Modelling

Normal behavior modeling is a data driven technique to define the baseline of an equipment or process. The concept relies heavily on extracting normal process data to train the model that will be used to pick future deviations from the baseline (Wu, et al., 2024). Most process and equipment data in our modern age is harnessed through a SCADA (Chesterman, et al., 2023). A SCADA consists of three main parts which are peripheral sensors (They get data from the surrounding environments), connections (They are used for transmissions), master computer (Used for data storage) and the human interaction interface (Chesterman, et al., 2023). Sensors do retrieve data from the peripheral parts of the equipment or process (Chesterman, et al., 2023). The data will be communicated to the master computer through communication cables, such as Ethernet cables. The master computer is responsible for data, as well as converting the data into readable format (Chalapathy & Chawla, 2019).

Since a NMB evolve around normal data, once the data is harnessed from a process or equipment, the abnormal will be dropped from the training data-set. The pre-processed data will be trained on by DL architectures (Wu, et al., 2024). The accuracy of the model will then be evaluated by checking model reconstruction losses. Higher reconstruction losses indicate a failure on training, while a low reconstruction loss indicate DL architecture ability to train effectively.(Chalapathy & Chawla, 2019; Wu, et al., 2024).

Figure 2 Normal behaviour Modelling Concept: (Wu, et al., 2024)

A threshold has to be defined from the model by understanding the statistical properties of the reconstruction loss in combination to expert knowledge. The threshold should be such, when anomalous data is processed through the model, reconstruction losses should be higher than the threshold (Wu, et al., 2024). When everything is normal, the reconstruction losses should be lower than the Threshold (Wu, et al., 2024).

Figure 3 Concept of Anomaly Detection: Adopted from (Sparkcognition, 2022)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A laptop was used for to process the data that was extracted from the CDSE SCADA master computer. On this study an Asus Computer was used with the following features:

- 1) 11th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i3-1115G4 @ 3.00GHz 3.00GHz
- 2) Installed RAM 8.00 GB

A Jupiter notebook was used for processing the data. Tensorflow and Keras were used Deep Learning platforms of choice.

For the study, data from 20 production days was taken from the master computer from 18/03/25 to 18/04/25. This consists of 16 normal data sets and 4 anomalous data sets. Each day representing a single data set of between 17 000 entries to 25 000 entries. The 20 data sets were concatenated for easy manipulation with labels 0 to 4. Label 0 representing the normal data, Label 1 representing anomalous data_set of Main Motor Amperage, Label 2 representing anomalous data_set of Gearbox Temperature, Label 3 representing anomalous data_set of Barrel Section_2 temperature and Label 4 representing anomalous data_set of Barrel Section_3.

The original lay out of the original data set had the following features:

- 1) Operator set variables
- 2) CRVs
- 3) The operators set variable were later dropped and only CRVs were used for training

Table 1 Features of the dataset

Operator Set Variables	Critical Response Variables (CRVs)
Barrel Section 2 set value	Barrel Section 2
Barrel Section 3 set value	Barrel Section 3
Screw speed	Gearbox Temperate
Water dosage	Main Motor Amperage
Feed dosage	
Cutter speed	

The resulted data (Normal data set) was trained through three architectures which are RNN, RNN-LSTM and RNN-LSTM-DAE, which were all composed for 800 neurons, five layers

and prediction slide widow of 2. For uniform exposure to the training, the maximum Epoch was pegged at 50 and patience was defined at 5. The optimizer used on all architectures was ‘Adam’. The models were primarily evaluated based on overall test reconstruction loss and CRVs reconstruction losses.

RESULTS

The results of the study reported the outcome of the three architectures deployed for NBM development. The best deep learning architecture was picked with the least reconstruction losses both on overall and on CRVs level.

Overall Reconstruction losses

Table 2 Overall Reconstruction Loss of RNN, RNN-LSTM and RNN-LSTM-DAE

Architecture	Neurons	Training MSE	Test MSE	Slide	Time / Epoch	Time/ Step	Optimiser
RNN	800	2.0113×10^{-4}	1.0017×10^{-4}	2	201s	32s	Adam
RNN-LSTM	800	1.9685×10^{-4}	1.0009×10^{-4}	2	210s	29s	Adam
RNN-LSTM-DAE	800	1.2103×10^{-4}	1.0007×10^{-4}	2	150s	31s	Adam

According to the table above RNN-LSTM-DAE exhibited better results both on the overall training and overall test reconstruction losses.

CRV Reconstruction losses

To understand the reconstruction losses on each Response Critical Variable (CRV), reconstruction losses and graphs were retrieved from the modeling report of the test data.

Figure 4 Mean Reconstruction losses of CRVs

RNN-LSTM-DAE was the model that came with most CRVs with the least mean reconstruction losses on Barrel Section_3 temperature and Gearbox temperature CRVs. RNN-

LSTM only scored best on Main Motor Amperage and RNN only scored best on Barrel Section_2 Temperature.

Threshold determination

The thresholds of the NBM were determined by looking at CRVs reconstruction losses histogram and plot boxes for data distribution for each CRV. The threshold was just supposed to be slightly higher from normal reconstruction losses, but away from the outlier region. The following reconstruction losses were picked for their respective CRVs

Table 3 Threshold Values for CRVs

CRV	Threshold
Main Amperage Threshold	0.04
Gearbox Temperature	0.02
Barrel_2 Temperature	0.02
Barrel_3 Temperature	0.1

Evaluations of NBM using Anomalous Data Sets

To indicate the full effectiveness of the model, anomalies were to be highlighted on the normalized process data. Known anomalies were supposed to be picked. The following data sets were utilized for the exercise, anomalous data set_1 (Main Motor Amperage anomalies), anomalous data set_2 (Gearbox Temperature anomalies), anomalous data set_3 (Barrel Section_2 anomalies) and anomalous_4 (Barrel Section_3 anomalies).

CRV: Main Motor Amperage

The anomalous dataset of the main motor amperage was reported on 21032025, the operator and maintenance team noted amperage spikes that almost threaten the main driving motor to trip.

Figure 5 Main Motor Amperage anomalies from Anomalous dataset_1

The known anomalies were picked amongst other extrusion systematic anomalies. Hence the model was able to profoundly pick known anomalies on the Main Motor Amperage.

CRV: Gearbox Temperature

The anomalous data of the gearbox temperature was reported on 20250704, it was noted as a single spike in gearbox temperature.

Figure 6 Gearbox Temperature anomalies from Anomalous dataset_2

The reported known anomaly was picked amongst other extrusion related anomalies. Hence the model was able to profoundly pick known anomalies on the Gearbox Temperature.

CRV: Extruder Barrel Section_2

The anomalous data set of barrel section 2, which is anomalous data_set 3 was recorded on 20240411. It was reported as a spike in temperature that emanated from a gradual increase in barrel section_2 temperature.

Figure 7 Barrel Section_2 Temperature anomalies from Anomalous data_set 3

The model was capable of picking up the reported anomaly, amongst other extrusion systematic anomalies.

CRV: Extruder Barrel Section_3

The anomalous data set of barrel section 3, which is anomalous data_set 4 was recorded on 10042025. It was reported as a sudden spike in temperature which quickly subsided.

Figure 8 Barrel Section_3 Temperature anomalies from Anomalous data_set 4

The model was capable of picking up the reported anomaly, amongst other extrusion systematic anomalies.

DISCUSSION

Stacked models proved to work much better in NBM development of a CDSE machine. RNN-LSTM-DAE has the advantage of having various architectures fused together for different functionalities. RNN as an architecture is prone to vanishing and exploding gradients, which makes model learning less efficient (Mienye et al., 2024). LSTMs are known to improve the RNN in that respect, but unfortunately they don't deal with the noise in the data. For NBM deep learning auto encoders are known to be effective, because they remove noise. Hence having RNN, LSTM and DAE in the same architecture become a game changer (Mienye et al., 2024). The model will definitely train better and achieve better accuracy. This is what was evidenced by the results of the study.

Under the same conditions, the RNN-LSTM-DAE thrived better and produced a more competitive result than RNN and RNN LSTM. This made an effective and efficient NBM model for the CDSE. The model was capable of picking all known anomalies including other extrusion systematic anomalies which were not reported.

To fully get our NBM to work it was important to define thresholds. The histograms and plot box of the CRVs reconstruction losses were useful in communicating the distribution of data for a proper threshold picking. A higher threshold was going to mean that a lot of anomalies were going to be missed, at the same time a lower threshold meant that a lot of false anomalies

were going to be picked. Using known anomalies to check the effectiveness of the model was key to ensure that DL NBM was picking the right anomalies.

CONCLUSION

Though various RNN architectures can be deployed for NBM development, for a CDSE the RNN-LSTM-DAE was capable to out-perform other architectures both on overall and CRVs reconstruction. All known anomalies from four anomalous data sets representing anomalies of all four CRVs were positively picked, amongst other anomalies. This meant the model developed using RNN-LSTM-DAE was effective and efficient. This was ground breaking for predictive maintenance of a CDSE machine as anomalies were to be picked way before they become breakdowns, with root cause easy to conduct.

REFERANCES

1. Aminzadeh, A., Sattarpanah Karganroudi, S., Majidi, S., Dabompre, C., Azaiez, K., Mitride, C. and Sénéchal, E. 2025. A Machine Learning Implementation to Predictive Maintenance and Monitoring of Industrial Compressors. *Sensors* 25(4), p. 1006. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/25/4/1006> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
2. Chesterman, X., Verstraeten, T., Daems, P.-J., Nowé, A. and Helsen, J. 2023. Overview of normal behavior modeling approaches for SCADA-based wind turbine condition monitoring demonstrated on data from operational wind farms. *Wind Energy Science* 8(6), pp. 893–924. Available at: <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/8/893/2023/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
3. Chalapathy, R. and Chawla, S. 2019. Deep Learning for Anomaly Detection: A Survey. Available at: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.03407> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
4. Cho, H. & Lee, H. 2019. Biomedical named entity recognition using deep neural networks with contextual information. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 20(1): 735. <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-019-3321-4> 24 June 2025.
5. Cho, H. and Lee, H. 2019. Biomedical named entity recognition using deep neural networks with contextual information. *BMC Bioinformatics* 20(1), p. 735. Available at: <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-019-3321-4> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
6. Evermann, J., Rehse, J.-R. and Fettke, P. 2017. Predicting process behaviour using deep learning. *Decision Support Systems* 100, pp. 129–140. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0167923617300635> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
7. Hatcher, W.G. and Yu, W. 2018. A Survey of Deep Learning: Platforms, Applications and Emerging Research Trends. *IEEE Access* 6, pp. 24411–24432. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8351898/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
8. Jankauskas, M. et al. 2023. Exploring the Limits of Early Predictive Maintenance in Wind Turbines Applying an Anomaly Detection Technique. *Sensors* 23(12), p. 5695. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/12/5695> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
9. Landauer, M., Onder, S., Skopik, F. and Wurzenberger, M. 2023. Deep learning for anomaly detection in log data: A survey. *Machine Learning with Applications* 12, p. 100470. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2666827023000233> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].

10. Lee, J.-H., Okwuosa, C.N. and Hur, J.-W. 2023. Extruder Machine Gear Fault Detection Using Auto encoder LSTM via Sensor Fusion Approach. *Inventions* 8(6), p. 140. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2411-5134/8/6/140> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
11. Lyons, J.T. and Göçmen, T. 2021. Applied Machine Learning Techniques for Performance Analysis in Large Wind Farms. *Energies* 14(13), p. 3756. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/14/13/3756> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
12. Magadza, T. and Viriri, S. 2021. Deep Learning for Brain Tumor Segmentation: A Survey of State-of-the-Art. *Journal of Imaging* 7(2), p. 19. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2313-433X/7/2/19> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
13. Maher, Y. and Danouj, B. 2020. Survey on Deep Learning applied to predictive maintenance. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)* 10(6), p. 5592. Available at: <http://ijece.iaescore.com/index.php/IJECE/article/view/21550> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
14. McKinnon, C., Turnbull, A., Koukoura, S., Carroll, J. and McDonald, A. 2020. Effect of Time History on Normal Behaviour Modelling Using SCADA Data to Predict Wind Turbine Failures. *Energies* 13(18), p. 4745. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/13/18/4745> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
15. Meyer, A. 2021. Multi-target normal behaviour models for wind farm condition monitoring. *Applied Energy* 300, p. 117342. Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0306261921007509> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
16. Mienye, I.D., Swart, T.G. and Obaido, G. 2024. Recurrent Neural Networks: A Comprehensive Review of Architectures, Variants, and Applications. *Information* 15(9), p. 517. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2078-2489/15/9/517> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
17. Namuduri, S., Narayanan, B.N., Davuluru, V.S.P., Burton, L. and Bhansali, S. 2020. Review—Deep Learning Methods for Sensor Based Predictive Maintenance and Future Perspectives for Electrochemical Sensors. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 167(3), p. 037552. Available at: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1149/1945-7111/ab67a8> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
18. Pang, G., Shen, C., Cao, L. and Hengel, A.V.D. 2022. Deep Learning for Anomaly Detection: A Review. *ACM Computing Surveys* 54(2), pp. 1–38. Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3439950> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
19. Pattlolla, S.S.S., Krupa Lakshman, D., Shekar Yadav, D., Anshu Kumar, G. and V Appalanaidu, M. 2024. Predictive Maintenance of Industrial Equipment Using Data Science. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Available at: <https://www.ssrn.com/abstract=4840169> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
20. Perera, Y.S., Li, J., Kelly, A.L. and Abeykoon, C. 2023. Melt Pressure Prediction in Polymer Extrusion Processes with Deep Learning. In: *2023 European Control Conference (ECC)*. Bucharest, Romania: IEEE, pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10178125/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
21. Qais, M.H., Kewat, S., Loo, K.H., Lai, C.-M. and Leung, A. 2023. LSTM-Based Stacked Autoencoders for Early Anomaly Detection in Induction Heating Systems. *Mathematics* 11(15), p. 3319. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/11/15/3319> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
22. Sparkcognition. 2022. Predictive Maintenance Using Normal Behavior Modeling [White Paper]. Available at: <https://aicorporate.nz/Resource/Embed/117084>

23. Sule, S., Okafor, G.I., Momoh, O.C., Gbaa, S.T. & Amonyeze, A.O. 2024. Applications of food extrusion technology. *MOJ Food Processing & Technology*, 12(1): 74–84. <https://medcraveonline.com/MOJFPT/applications-of-food-extrusion-technology.html> 11 July 2025.
24. Turnbull, A., Carroll, J. and McDonald, A. 2022. A Comparative Analysis on the Variability of Temperature Thresholds through Time for Wind Turbine Generators Using Normal Behaviour Modelling. *Energies* 15(14), p. 5298. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/15/14/5298> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
25. Wiese, T.L. 2024. Predictive Maintenance Using Artificial Intelligence in Critical Infrastructure: A Decision-Making Framework. *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management* 8(4), pp. 01–04. Available at: <https://aipublications.com/ijebm/detail/predictive-maintenance-using-artificial-intelligence-in-critical-infrastructure-a-decision-making-framework/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
26. Wong, L., Liu, D., Berti-Equille, L., Alnegheimish, S. and Veeramachaneni, K. 2022. AER: Auto-Encoder with Regression for Time Series Anomaly Detection. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*. Osaka, Japan: IEEE, pp. 1152–1161. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10020857/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
27. Wu, H., Badihi, H., Xue, Y. and Vilkkko, M. 2024. A Normal Behavior Model Based on Machine Learning for Wind Turbine Cyber-Attack Detection. In: *2024 International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Energy Transformation (AIE)*. Vaasa, Finland: IEEE, pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10561323/> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].
28. Yuan, L., Qiu, L. and Zhang, C. 2022. Research on Normal Behavior Models for Status Monitoring and Fault Early Warning of Pitch Motors. *Applied Sciences* 12(15), p. 7747. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/12/15/7747> [Accessed: 19 April 2025].